

Immersive Virtual Reality and Spatial Navigation: The Impacts of ADHD

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Abstract

Spatial navigation is a complex task that is dependent on several cognitive processes that can be hard to measure and replicate in traditional in-lab experiments. In comparison, immersive virtual reality proves to be a means to simulate real world contexts with enhanced ecological validity and spatial embodiment. As a result, immersive virtual reality continues to prove to be a useful tool to study spatial navigation. This research seeks to understand the impacts of executive dysfunction, present in ADHD adults, on navigational abilities and spatial learning. This study consists of two experimental tasks. The first is a wayfinding task, where participants are asked to traverse an urban virtual geographic environment and locate waypoints in a specified order according to a provided map. This task consists of ten levels that progressively get more difficult. The second task drops participants at a semi-random point in the environment they just traversed and asks them to orient themselves to the starting location; this heading orientation task tests participants' spatial learning. Unlike traditional assessments, xR allows researchers to observe navigation behaviors dynamically, capturing how individuals with ADHD manage challenges like spatial working memory, attention, and cognitive load capacity during complex spatial tasks. This is particularly important for understanding how executive dysfunction affects real-world functioning and for tailoring environments or interventions to better support individuals with neurodivergent cognitive profiles. We hypothesize that as the wayfinding task increases in difficulty, we will see a divergence in participant performance with ADHD adults performing worse on all measures. This research will contribute to countering spatial deskilling and the development of neuro-adaptive navigational aids that support safety, efficiency, and spatial learning.

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